

AN INVESTIGATION INTO KEY RISK FACTORS OF HEART DISEASE AND THEIR PREDICTIVE POWER

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Abstract

The high prevalence of cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) is a global concern. Early identification and effective management are crucial goals for healthcare services. However, most clinically used methods and machine learning models for prediction emphasize secondary risk factors, considering only a limited number of attributes. These models may overlook the early stages of the disease by neglecting behavioral risk factors, which eventually manifest as physical symptoms. Early detection of cardiovascular disease facilitates easier and more effective treatment. To enhance prediction accuracy, it is essential to identify novel risk factors or refine existing ones. In today's information age, large amount of medical data is available. With Feature extraction, we can enhance model performance, captures complex relationships and improves generalization. we can better identify individuals who might otherwise be misclassified as low risk.

Keywords: Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs), machine learning, behavioral risk factors, Feature extraction.

Introduction

Heart diseases are so prevalent today that almost every adult is aware of it. despite the awareness about the prevalence of the disease, it continues to be the leading cause of mortality worldwide. According to WHO, **Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) diseases** being the leading cause of death globally, takes an estimated 17.9 million lives each year. CVDs are a group of disorders of the heart and blood vessels and include coronary heart disease, cerebrovascular disease, rheumatic heart disease and other conditions. More than four out of five CVD deaths are due to heart attacks and strokes, and one third of these deaths occur prematurely in people under 70 years of age.

Cardiovascular disease refers to all the diseases of the circulatory system (heart and blood vessels). These include diseases such as: coronary heart disease, stroke, myocardial arrhythmia, and heart failure. The main cause of many of these diseases is atherosclerosis, which refers to the build up of fat and plaque inside the arteries, which can block the blood

vessel. A blockage can result in the death of cells that were relying on these arteries for their oxygen supply – such as in a heart attack.

Coronary heart disease includes heart attacks and angina. While a heart attack results from momentary blockage of the artery to a section of heart muscle, angina results from a partial blockage and produces chest pain, particularly on exertion. A Stroke is a temporary blockage of the blood vessels to the brain, resulting in the death of some brain cells, or a vessel begins to bleed, reducing the delivery of oxygen to part of the brain. Stroke (cerebrovascular disease) can result in a range of debilitations including: communication, mobility, thinking and can also be fatal. Heart failure is a condition where the heart is unable to maintain a strong enough blood flow. It can result in chronic tiredness, reduced capacity for physical activity and shortness of breath. It is a life-threatening condition and cannot be cured in most cases.

In individuals, we can classify the risk factors as follows: 1. Background risk factors (age, sex, genetic composition, level of education.) 2. Behavioral risk factors (tobacco use, unhealthy diet, physical inactivity) 3. Intermediate risk factors (elevated blood lipids, diabetes, high blood pressure, overweight/obesity). The surprising fact is that Cardiovascular diseases are primarily caused by Behavioral risk factors, hence are preventable by changing our lifestyle.

Literature review

The industrialization of the economy with a resultant shift from physically demanding to sedentary jobs, along with the current consumerism and technology-driven culture that is related to longer work hours, longer commutes, and less leisure time for recreational activities, may explain the significant and steady increase in the rates of CVD during the last few decades. Specifically, physical inactivity, intake of a high-calorie diet, saturated fats, and sugars are associated with the development of atherosclerosis and other metabolic disturbances like metabolic syndrome, diabetes mellitus, and hypertension that are highly prevalent in people with CVD.

In a study conducted by Muhammad Salman Pathan in 2022, “Analyzing the impact of feature selection on the accuracy of heart disease prediction”¹ the impact of feature selection techniques on the performance of ML models is observed. The analysis was performed for CVD and Framingham heart disease datasets. Filter-based feature selection technique namely the ANOVA-F test is employed to identify the most important features from the datasets for an effective heart disease prediction. It is observed that features like age, hypertension, glucose, previous heart disease, and blood pressure were found to reflect the most important risk factors for heart disease except the traditional factors using both datasets. It is concluded that using the feature selection only the most important features related to heart disease are selected which reduces the computational complexities and improve the accuracy of prediction models.

According to Yusuf S, Hawken S, “Effect of potentially modifiable risk factors associated with myocardial infarction in 52 countries (the INTERHEART study)”², a study that included subjects from 52 countries, including high, middle, and low-income countries, 9 modifiable risks factors accounted for 90% of the risk of having a first MI: smoking, dyslipidemia, hypertension, diabetes, abdominal obesity, psychosocial factors, consumption of fruits and vegetables, regular alcohol consumption, and physical inactivity. It is important to mention that in this study 36% of the population-attributable risk of MI was accounted to smoking.

Björn Zethelius , “Use of multiple biomarkers to improve the prediction of death from cardiovascular causes” PMID: 18480203 DOI: 10.1056/NEJMoa0707064. This suggest that in elderly men with or without prevalent cardiovascular disease, the simultaneous addition of several biomarkers of cardiovascular and renal abnormalities substantially improves the risk stratification for death from cardiovascular causes beyond that of a model that is based only on established risk factors

Materials and Methods:

In our study we used a dataset which was available online from Kaggle. This data set dates from 1988 and consists of four databases: Cleveland, Hungary, Switzerland, and Long Beach V. It contains 76 attributes, including the predicted attribute, but all published experiments refer to using a subset of 14 of them. The "target" field refers to the presence of heart disease in the patient. It is integer valued 0 = no disease and 1 = disease.

```
data.head()
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	age	sex	cp	trestbps	chol	fbs	restecg	thalach	exang	oldpeak	slope	ca	thal	target
0	52	1	0	125	212	0	1	168	0	1.0	2	2	3	0
1	53	1	0	140	203	1	0	155	1	3.1	0	0	3	0
2	70	1	0	145	174	0	1	125	1	2.6	0	0	3	0
3	61	1	0	148	203	0	1	161	0	0.0	2	1	3	0
4	62	0	0	138	294	1	1	106	0	1.9	1	3	2	0

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data.tail()
```

	age	sex	cp	trestbps	chol	fbs	restecg	thalach	exang	oldpeak	slope	ca	thal	target
1020	59	1	1	140	221	0	1	164	1	0.0	2	0	2	1
1021	60	1	0	125	258	0	0	141	1	2.8	1	1	3	0
1022	47	1	0	110	275	0	0	118	1	1.0	1	1	2	0
1023	50	0	0	110	254	0	0	159	0	0.0	2	0	2	1
1024	54	1	0	120	188	0	1	113	0	1.4	1	1	3	0

The image above shows the data samples used for our study.

Attribute Information:

- 1 age
- 2 sex
- 3 chest pain type (4 values)
- 4 resting blood pressure
- 5 serum cholestorol in mg/dl
- 6 fasting blood sugar > 120 mg/dl
- 7 resting electrocardiographic results (values 0,1,2)
- 8 maximum heart rate achieved
- 9 exercise induced angina
- 10 oldpeak = ST depression induced by exercise relative to rest
- 11 the slope of the peak exercise ST segment
- 12 number of major vessels (0-3) colored by flourosopy
- 13 thal:0=normal;1=fixed defect; 2 = reversable defect

The names and social security numbers of the patients were recently removed from the database, replaced with dummy values.

To identify the impact of each of these factors and how they are inter-related,we used correlation matrix.

	age	sex	cp	trestbps	chol	fbs	restecg	thalach	exang	oldpeak	slope	ca	thal	target
age	1.000000	-0.103240	-0.071966	0.271121	0.219823	0.121243	-0.132696	-0.390227	0.088163	0.208137	-0.169105	0.271551	0.072297	-0.229324
sex	-0.103240	1.000000	-0.041119	-0.078974	-0.198258	0.027200	-0.055117	-0.049365	0.139157	0.084687	-0.026666	0.111729	0.198424	-0.279501
cp	-0.071966	-0.041119	1.000000	0.038177	-0.081641	0.079294	0.043581	0.306839	-0.401513	-0.174733	0.131633	-0.176206	-0.163341	0.434854
trestbps	0.271121	-0.078974	0.038177	1.000000	0.127977	0.181767	-0.123794	-0.039264	0.061197	0.187434	-0.120445	0.104554	0.059276	-0.138772
chol	0.219823	-0.198258	-0.081641	0.127977	1.000000	0.026917	-0.147410	-0.021772	0.067382	0.064880	-0.014248	0.074259	0.100244	-0.099966
fbs	0.121243	0.027200	0.079294	0.181767	0.026917	1.000000	-0.104051	-0.008866	0.049261	0.010859	-0.061902	0.137156	-0.042177	-0.041164
restecg	-0.132696	-0.055117	0.043581	-0.123794	-0.147410	-0.104051	1.000000	0.048411	-0.065606	-0.050114	0.086086	-0.078072	-0.020504	0.134468
thalach	-0.390227	-0.049365	0.306839	-0.039264	-0.021772	-0.008866	0.048411	1.000000	-0.380281	-0.349796	0.395308	-0.207888	-0.098068	0.422895
exang	0.088163	0.139157	-0.401513	0.061197	0.067382	0.049261	-0.065606	-0.380281	1.000000	0.310844	-0.267335	0.107849	0.197201	-0.438029
oldpeak	0.208137	0.084687	-0.174733	0.187434	0.064880	0.010859	-0.050114	-0.349796	0.310844	1.000000	-0.575189	0.221816	0.202672	-0.438441
slope	-0.169105	-0.026666	0.131633	-0.120445	-0.014248	-0.061902	0.086086	0.395308	-0.267335	-0.575189	1.000000	-0.073440	-0.094090	0.345512
ca	0.271551	0.111729	-0.176206	0.104554	0.074259	0.137156	-0.078072	-0.207888	0.107849	0.221816	-0.073440	1.000000	0.149014	-0.382085
thal	0.072297	0.198424	-0.163341	0.059276	0.100244	-0.042177	-0.020504	-0.098068	0.197201	0.202672	-0.094090	0.149014	1.000000	-0.337838
target	-0.229324	-0.279501	0.434854	-0.138772	-0.099966	-0.041164	0.134468	0.422895	-0.438029	-0.438441	0.345512	-0.382085	-0.337838	1.000000

A correlation matrix is a statistical technique used to evaluate the relationship between two variables in a data set. The matrix is a table in which every cell contains a correlation coefficient, where 1 is considered a strong relationship between variables, 0 a neutral relationship and -1 a not strong relationship.

As per the above definition, the target shows positive correlation of 0.434 with chest pain(cp), 0.1344 with restecg, 0.422 with thalach, and 0.3455 with slope.

Traditional Risk Factors identified from literature review were:

Age and Gender

The risk of heart disease increases with age due to the gradual buildup of plaque in the arteries. Men generally have a higher risk than women, although the risk for women increases post-menopause (American Heart Association, 2019).

Hypertension and Cholesterol

High blood pressure and elevated cholesterol levels are critical risk factors. The National Cholesterol Education Program (NCEP) emphasizes the role of cholesterol management in preventing heart disease (NCEP, 2002).

Lifestyle Factors

Smoking, physical inactivity, and poor dietary habits significantly contribute to heart disease risk. The WHO highlights that lifestyle modifications can substantially reduce the risk of heart disease (WHO, 2020).

Whereas, our study shows that chest pain(cp),restecg,thalach and slope are highly correlated with heart disease and can be used in feature selection to increase predictive performance.

By considering the result from above matrix we can select appropriate features for machine learning algorithms.

Machine learning (ML) is a subset of artificial intelligence (AI) that focuses on the development of algorithms and statistical models that enable computers to perform tasks without explicit instructions. Instead, these algorithms learn from and make predictions or decisions based on data. Machine learning is broadly categorized into supervised learning, unsupervised learning, and reinforcement learning. Supervised learning, which includes tasks like classification and regression, uses labeled datasets to train models. Unsupervised learning, such as clustering and association, deals with data without predefined labels, aiming to find hidden patterns or intrinsic structures. Reinforcement learning focuses on making sequences of decisions by optimizing cumulative rewards.

Findings and Analysis:

It shows from the above work that CVDs are primarily caused by behavioral risk factors which eventually manifest into physical symptoms. Hence, by incorporating lifestyle factors into the prediction criteria, we can detect them at early stages and the sooner we detect, the easier it is to treat.

Also, the use of accurate attributes in prediction offers several advantages over simply increasing training data. By focusing on attribute quality, machine learning models can achieve higher performance, reduce over-fitting, enhance interpretability, optimize resource

efficiency, and improve generalization to new data. This is particularly beneficial when working with large datasets, as it reduces the computational burden of model training and inference.

Finally, having this awareness people feel empowered knowing that there is something they can do about it in terms of their lifestyle choices.

Recommendations:

Regularly update predictive models based on new research findings and real-world data. Continuously monitor the effectiveness of models and refine them to improve accuracy and utility.

Conclusions:

In our studied, as a result of data analysis using correlation matrix we identified that chest pain(cp),restecg,thalach and slope are highly correlated with heart disease and can be used in feature selection to increase predictive performance.

Also, Incorporating behavioral risk factors into heart disease prediction models represents a significant advancement in early detection and prevention efforts. By broadening the scope of risk assessment to include lifestyle and behavioral factors, healthcare providers can identify at-risk individuals earlier, tailor interventions more effectively, and ultimately reduce the incidence and impact of cardiovascular diseases.

References:

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